

Deliverable D-JRP1-1.7

Work Package 1

Responsible Partner: Anses

Contributing partners: Anses, APHA, BfR, DTU, IZSLT, NVI, PIWET, RIVM, SSI, SVA, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP1-1.7: Publication in peer-reviewed journal
Project Acronym	IMPART
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Due month of the report	24
Actual submission month	38
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.;</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R Save date: 23/02/2021
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT): Confidential until publication in a scientific journal

Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
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IMPART WP1- SELECTIVE ISOLATION, DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF COLISTIN-RESISTANT ENTEROBACTERIACEAE

D-JRP1-1.7 Publication in peer-reviewed journal

The present document describes what is in progress in the deliverable D-JRP1-1.7 of the work package 1 of IMPART project.

The WP1 aimed to define and validate a method to selectively isolate, detect and characterize acquired colistin-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* (*mcr*-producing strains) in samples from food-producing animals. A pre-ring trial was performed to analyze the performance of different selective culture methods described in the literature through a multicenter evaluation including four participants. After results analysis, an alternative protocol was designed to improve the detection of colistin-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* and performance were assessed in a final multicenter evaluation (ring trial) with eleven participants. Both in the pre-ring trial and in the final ring trial, caecal content and meat samples were artificially contaminated with characterized *mcr*-producing strains originated from animals. Panels of samples and commercially selective agar plates to be tested were shipped to the WP1 participants with attached the protocol to be used and the result sheet to be filled in. Homogeneity and stability of the samples were assessed at Anses-Fougères laboratory the day of shipment and one day after reception and analysis of the samples was performed by the participating laboratories following the instructions in the protocol. Performance of the methods have been evaluated by calculating the sensitivity and the specificity parameters.

All the results and analysis of pre-ring trial and ring trial have been evaluated and published in two individual reports uploaded on the EJP website and Zenodo platform (D-JRP1-1.3 and D-JRP1-1.6).

The publication of WP1 results in peer-reviewed journal is in preparation. The deliverable D-JRP1-1.7 has been delayed because of unforeseen circumstances as health problems of the WP1 leader (long-term absence still ongoing) and Covid-19 pandemic situation. The journal have been chosen and the paper is in progress. As soon as the draft manuscript is written, the participants of the WP1 will be asked to feedback. The submission is expected to April 2021.